

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF STUDENTS WITH VISION PROBLEMS

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Abstract. *This article is about the psychological processes of social adaptation of students with vision problems and is aimed at psychologically practical help in social adaptation of blind students studying in boarding schools.*

Keywords: *visually impaired students, boarding school, psychologist, social adaptation, education, typhlopsychology, typhlopedagogue, rehabilitation, integration.*

Today, attention to the education of young people in the society is changing more and more. Integration of young people with disabilities into a healthy society depends on the conditions and services created in the state. In the countries of the world, systematic work is being carried out to protect the rights of persons with disabilities, to introduce comfortable conditions for their living, and to protect their work. In this regard, in recent years, a number of practical works have been launched in our country to protect the rights of persons with disabilities, protect their work, and take their place in society.

The integration of people with physical disabilities into a healthy society depends on the opportunities created in society. Undoubtedly, the role of education in learning the necessary professions for a person to take his place in society is extremely important. In this regard, the general secondary education system performs the main tasks in learning the most important life knowledge skills in the formation of a person as a person. First of all, no one can deny that the growing young generation is a process that depends on the effective product of education.

In recent years, the attention of our government to young people with disabilities is increasingly changing in a positive direction. In particular, specific measures are being taken to ensure that this category of youth takes a proper place in the society through vocational training and integration into an inclusive and healthy society.

"The psyche of blind and visually impaired people is, as usual, a unity of subjective and objective. It reflects the objective reality, which is reflected separately in the mind of each person. In fact, any event, any thought, any feeling is reflected in people's minds differently, subjectively, depending on experience, knowledge, attitude, need, mental and physical condition. And at the same time, the images, thoughts and feelings that appear in the mind more or less adequately reflect the objective reality. The study of the psyche of the blind and visually impaired compared to the study of the psyche of people with normal vision, in addition to the universal subjectivity of its manifestation, with the presence of regularities in the formation of mental functions and personal characteristics it gets complicated. The process of determining the general laws and specific features of the psyche of the blind and visually impaired becomes complicated, especially when visual defects are complicated by cytological changes in other parts of the body. Among the defects accompanying blindness and low vision, motor system disorders, reduced hearing and tactile acuity, and speech disorders are common. Serious intellectual disabilities, neuropsychic abnormalities, and psychophysical infantilism are also common among the blind and visually

impaired. At the same time, the percentage of cases of low vision complicated by blindness and other defects tends to increase. This is due to a decrease in cases of visual impairment due to injuries and a number of common and infectious diseases. On the other hand, it is associated with a relatively high number of cases of vision impairment due to various diseases of the central nervous system, congenital and hereditary vision pathologies. Currently, congenital and hereditary forms of visual pathology cause blindness in about 90% of cases.

The education of visually impaired students depends on their ability to properly communicate with others, overcome various psychological threats, and their psychological preparation. In this regard, it is important for psychologists and pedagogues working in special boarding schools to determine the mental health of each blind student and to eliminate the problems hindering their work through various psychological measures.

For this, psychologists in special boarding schools should perform the following tasks.

1. Continuous organization of individual interviews with each blind student admitted to a special boarding school;
2. Systematic development and implementation of the psychological questionnaire of students;
3. Regularly conduct psychological training sessions with depressed students;
4. Establish cooperation between the school psychologist and the public in solving the problems faced by blind students.

"Russian psychologist A.N.Leontev emphasizes the existence of mental and practical forms of human activity, the child's mind grows precisely in educational activities. D.B.Elkonin shows the characteristics of educational activity and emphasizes that it is social according to its essence, content and form of self-expression. Educational activity is such an activity, as a result of which, first of all, a change occurs in the student. Its product should be built on the basis of various motives. These motives should be directly related to the growth and development of the student's personality. Educational activity is directly related to the concepts of education, study and learning"[2].

The science that studies the psyche of blind children and their mental processes is the science of typhlopsychology. The science of typhlopsychology serves to study the mental world of blind people, their emotional experiences, to be mentally refreshed, and to realize their social adaptation in life. Psychologists and pedagogues working in special boarding schools should set themselves the goal of better learning the science of typhlopsychology, studying scientific researches and scientific innovations of the science. In this regard, the improvement of intuitive perception and imagination of a visually impaired student is greatly helped by psychological training sessions to eliminate abstract concepts.

"The complexity and difficulty of studying the psychology of the blind and blind is that this defect differs from one another in its diversity, level, and depth. From this point of view, visually impaired children and individuals can be divided into two groups, taking into account when the blindness occurred:

1. Those who were born blind and those who became blind and weak as a result of various negative impressions before the age of three.
2. Those who acquired visual impairment after three years of age. The main criterion for dividing visually impaired people into such groups is the amount of life experience and vision the child has accumulated during the period of eye health (if there was such a period).

The first group mainly includes blind and partially sighted people before the appearance of speech, who have no or very little visual imagination and experience.

The second group includes those who are blind and visually impaired after the age of three, and have more or less visual images and visual memory. It should also be pointed out that the visual perception of people with late blindness does not differ from that of healthy people[3].

"A.N. Leontiev shows the multidimensionality of images that serve as a systematic formation. The main levels of figurative representation of the surrounding world are emotional-cognitive, ideational and verbal-logical, which play an important role in the control and integration of emotional information.

Images of objects are formed on the basis of combining information from all sensory modalities. In most forms of figurative reflection, the leading role belongs to the visual modality (image visualization). Forming an image is an active process, during which more complete and deeper information is "extracted" from the reality surrounding the child. The content of the image is constantly enriched, clarified and adapted. This mainly happens in the process of mastering various types of effective activities of the child. There are three ways of forming ideas about objects: effective, figurative and symbolic. Early and preschool age should be used as the most sensitive age for acquiring images of surrounding objects and their speech design[4].

"In typhlopsychology and typhlopedagogy, the authors note that visual impairment affects the process of interpersonal interaction, activity, including social activity, the system of value orientations, the social formation (directly and indirectly) of a person. there are studies that prove negative effects on important characteristics, qualities and professional self-determination. (A.G.Litvak, G.V.Nikulina, L.I.Solntseva, V.A.Feoktistova and others). The work under review shows that these characteristics are related to specific components of social maturity, and therefore conditions of visual deprivation may have a negative impact on the development of social maturity of visually impaired individuals[5].

The mental alertness and social readiness of every visually impaired student studying in an educational institution depends on the level and effectiveness of the psychological measures implemented in the educational institution. For this purpose, every psychologist should draw up prospective plans for the coming years, develop a strategy for dealing with students in a difficult situation.

Research in the field of typhlopsychology and typhlopedagogy shows that many preschool children with visual impairments face significant difficulties in the process of interpersonal communication, which negatively affects the communication process itself and its effectiveness (L.S.Volkova, G.V.Grigorieva, V.Z.Deniskin, M.Zaorska, M.I.Zemtsova, I.G.Kornilova, I.V.Novichkova, L.I.Plaksia, L.I.Solntseva, S.V.Tarskikh, N.A.Yakovleva and others.). If such a child does not receive the necessary help from adults in time, he will gradually develop inappropriate behavior that does not correspond to the events happening around him, and will lead to incorrect adaptation in society[6].

"In the course of rehabilitation work on socio-psychological adaptation (readaptation) of the blind, practitioners in special institutions (schools, rehabilitation centers, rehabilitation rooms) face certain difficulties. There is a need to overcome the depression that appears as a reaction to blindness, to form an adequate attitude towards others, one's disability and one's activities.

At the first stage of socio-psychological adjustment, it is necessary to consider the overcoming of depression associated with the awareness of the defect, to which visually impaired

people have a very painful attitude. The depth and duration of the reaction depends on the characteristics of the person, as well as the speed of the disease, its severity and the time of its onset. The most serious mental injuries are observed in elderly blind people. Those who are blinded instantly have a more severe reaction than those who lose their vision gradually. However, the practice of rehabilitation shows that even in such cases, involving the blind in activities allows them to get rid of depression and restore an optimistic attitude to life".[7]

Pre-school classes are organized in boarding schools where blind children are educated, and the admission of young children to these groups is carried out in a systematic way. It is advisable to have direct psychological observation with them and give them the necessary advice until they finish the boarding school.

In our opinion, the meaningful aspect of social rehabilitation of blind and visually impaired children in a special (corrective) school includes implementation of rehabilitation activities in three directions:

- a) psychological-pedagogical rehabilitation (learning to read and write according to the L. Braille system, obtaining the necessary level of general and additional school education, learning knowledge, skills and self-control development of an active life position);
- b) cultural and household rehabilitation (training in self-service and orientation skills, aesthetic education);
- c) social and labor rehabilitation (vocational guidance, vocational training and employment).

Through the systematic implementation of psychological rehabilitation in boarding schools, it positively helps blind students to successfully complete the processes of preparing them for social life. Proper organization of activities can help solve many problems. When students studying in an educational institution are mentally refreshed, it will have a positive effect on their independent life in the future, and their rightful place in society.

It is necessary to develop psychological educational programs suitable for blind students studying in special boarding schools, to achieve their inclusive connection with a healthy life. For this, it is necessary to analyze the psychological changes of each student and study his mental state. Only then will we have the right approach to preparing each student for life.

The number of works devoted to the formation of a healthy lifestyle in blind children is very small, they are devoted only to some aspects of this problem. The analysis of educational programs and practical experience allows to see that there are still no programmatic and methodological developments for children with visual impairments that would allow them to form the foundations of a healthy lifestyle, taking into account primary defects and secondary developmental disorders.[9]

"The famous scientist-psychologist L.S. Vygotsky said that the main task of education is to bring an abnormal child to life, to correct his social dislocation, that is, to eliminate deviations in behavior that determine the social image of a person. In this regard, he wrote: "Perhaps, sooner or later, humanity will overcome blindness, deafness, and insanity. But it defeats them much faster not medically and biologically, but socially and pedagogically." L.S. Vygotsky actively developed the idea of the compensatory ability of the abnormal child's body. He considered the starting point of correctional-pedagogical work with abnormal children to be the preserved state of the child's body, the least affected by the anomaly or not affected by it".[10]

In our opinion, it is no exaggeration to say that the time has come to create training programs and methodical manuals for this activity. Taking into account the above, I would like to make the following suggestions and recommendations:

1. Raising the educational professional training of psychologists working in special boarding schools for blind children to modern levels;
2. Creating educational programs and manuals that help psychologists develop their skills;
3. Improving the work of the most experienced psychologists by popularizing their work;
4. Organization of psychological activities among boarding school psychologists throughout the Republic on issues of preparing blind children for life;
5. Systematic establishment of mutual cooperation with state and non-state public organizations so that every graduating blind youth can find their place in independent life.

In conclusion, preparing young people with visual impairments for life, adapting them psychologically to society is urgent today. In this regard, if all pedagogues and psychologists working in educational institutions conscientiously perform their duties and continuously develop their activities, many problems will undoubtedly be solved. Based on the correct organization of correctional training sessions for visually impaired students who are depressed and struggling to find their place in an independent life, harmoniously connect them with social life. we can achieve full integration of students with society.

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